

PROPERTIES OF DIALYSED HYDROUS ALUMINA HYDROSOLS. PART II. TITRATION WITH BASES AND ACIDS.

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Potentiometric titrations have been carried out with acids and bases. Buffering is maximum at p_H 11.2 with NaOH; at p_H 11.0 with Ba(OH)₂ and at p_H 10.8 with Ca(OH)₂. A weak inflexion point has been observed at p_H 12.2 and the buffer index curve shows a minimum at this point. The amount of alumina coming into true solution increases with the concentration of alkali and complete solution occurs at the inflexion point at p_H 12.2. Titration of aluminium chloride with NaOH shows an inflexion near p_H 11.0 corresponding to the complete solution of precipitated alumina. The p_H at which this inflexion point occurs, however, depends on the age of the precipitate. HCl is totally adsorbed at small concentrations. A strong buffer action indicating true solution is observed at p_H 3.5, 3.4, 3.0 and 2.8 for acetic, phosphoric, oxalic and sulphuric acids respectively.

There is some difference of opinion as to whether a solution of aluminium hydroxide in alkalis is to be regarded as a case of true solution or of peptisation (Hildebrand, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 864; Blum, *ibid.*, 1913, 35, 1499; Britton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2120; Miller, *Colloid Symposium Monograph*, 1925, 3, 208; Mahin, Ingraham and Stewart, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 35, 30; 1914, 36, 2381; Davis and Farnham, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 1057; Dhar and Chatterji, *Chem. News*, 1920, 121, 253). In the present paper colloidal hydrous alumina and aluminium chloride solutions have been titrated potentiometrically with bases-NaOH, Ba(OH)₂, Ca(OH)₂ and Mg(OH)₂ and acids-HCl, H₂SO₄, H₃PO₄, H₂C₂O₄ and CH₃COOH.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The preparation of the sols and the experimental technique used have been described in Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 159). Duplicated titrations show good agreement (Fig. 1, curves 1 and 2, 4 and 5; Fig. 2, curves 8, 9, 10 and 11). For ultrafiltration perforated porcelain bed and 'cella' finest membranes have been used. Aluminium has been estimated in the ultrafiltrates according to the method of Berg (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1927, 71, 369) by 8-oxyquinoline. A water thermostat has been used at $35 \pm .05^\circ$.

Titration with Bases.

The sols used in this work are the same as have been described in Part I. The results are given in Figs. 1—4. On the addition of a base the p_n increases at first very sharply but thereafter its change indicates a strong buffer action. Sol A (Fig. 1, curves 1 and 2) shows a weak inflexion point at p_n 6.2 which should be attributed to dissolved hydrochloric acid or adsorbed aluminium chloride and the titration curve of its

FIG. 1.

Hydrous alumina sol A—titration with bases.

ultrafiltrate with NaOH (Fig. 1, curve 6) gives a total acidity of $3 \times 10^{-3}N$. Strong buffering is observed near p_n 11.25 with NaOH, at p_n 11.0 with $Ba(OH)_2$, and at p_n 10.8 with $Ca(OH)_2$ (Fig. 2). With NaOH a weak

inflexion point and complete solution of alumina has been obtained by proceeding up to p_H value as high as 12.5 (Fig. 3, curve 13). But no such inflexion point and complete solution has been observed with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ or $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, probably because very high p_H values could not be reached with these bases. The buffer indices for sol C are plotted in curves 8', 10' and 11' of Fig. 2. The buffer index rises slowly at first then rapidly and assumes infinite values indicating a very strong buffer action. In the case of NaOH (Fig. 3, curve 13') it is finally followed by a minimum indicating an inflexion corresponding to the neutralisation of an acid.

FIG. 2.

Hydrus alumina sol C—titration with bases.

Rabinowitsch and Wassiliev (*Kolloid Z.*, 1931, 56; 305) titrated aluminium hydroxide sols with KOH but the p_H at the horizontal part and the p_H at the inflexion point in their curve are different from those of the

curves given in this paper. It will be shown later that precipitates of the different 'age' show a difference in this p_H value.

Solutions of aluminium chloride have also been titrated with NaOH. The

FIG. 3.
Hydrous alumina sol II.

results given in Fig. 4 show that the curves are of the same form as those obtained by Britton (*loc.cit.*) and Davis and Farnham (*loc.cit.*) but differ from those of Hildebrand (*loc.cit.*) and of Blum (*loc.cit.*) which have a weak inflexion point in their initial portion. Davis and Farnham (*loc.cit.*) ascribe this inflexion point to the free acid contained in the solutions used by them. Their opinion is confirmed by the titration curve (Fig. 4, curve 15) of an aluminium chloride solution to which some free acid has been added. On the addition of alkali the p_H at first rises sharply and when particles of alumina appear, the p_H remains almost constant between 3.5 and 4.0 as long as

alumina continues to be precipitated. This p_H of precipitation depends on the initial p_H of the $AlCl_3$ solution (Fig. 4, curves 16, 17 and 18). When all the alumina has been precipitated, the p_H again rises and the titration curve shows a sharp inflexion at p_H about 7.6. A second inflexion point corresponding to the solution of alumina is observed at p_H about 10.9. It has been found that alumina precipitated by small additions of alkali inside the titration cell when kept for sufficient time (about 12 hours) cannot

be easily dissolved even with larger concentration of alkali (Fig. 4, curve 18). The titrations were therefore carried out by measuring the p_H of a definite volume of the sol contained in separate Jena glass bottles to which increasing amounts of alkali had been added.

FIG. 4.

$AlCl_3$ solution—titration with NaOH.

Aluminium has been estimated in the ultrafiltrates of sol C corresponding to different stages in its titration with bases. Results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Sol C. (20 c.c. of sol = 25.5 mg. of Al_2O_3).

Sodium hydroxide.			Barium hydroxide.		
Conc. of alkali.	p_H .	Amount in 20 c.c. of sol.	Conc. of alkali	p_H .	Amount in 20 c.c. of sol.
$10.95 \times 10^{-3}N$	11.35	0.65 mg.	$11.65 \times 10^{-3}N$	11.54	0.04 mg.
33.45	11.97	1.65	21.71	11.84	0.13
42.95	12.09	3.80	51.14	12.20	0.29
50.04	12.19	4.20	70.09	12.25	0.43
55.40	12.23	4.82			

The amount of alumina coming into solution increases as the p_H rises but more so for NaOH than for $Ba(OH)_2$ compared at the same p_H .

Hildebrand (*loc. cit.*) and Blum (*loc. cit.*) titrated aluminium sols with alkalis and obtained an inflexion point near p_H 11.0 at which p_H they found that the solution was free from particles of colloidal dimensions. They concluded that a definite compound namely $NaAlO_2$ was formed. Britton (*loc. cit.*) also considers this inflexion point to denote the formation of aluminates. Mahin, Ingraham and Stewart (*loc. cit.*) hold that the colloidal properties of aluminium hydroxide play such an important part in conditioning its solubility in bases that there is room for doubt whether the alleged aluminates exist as definite salts at all. Dhar and Chatterji (*loc. cit.*) observed that the conductivity of a solution of sodium hydroxide was not appreciably changed by the addition of aluminium hydroxide and concluded that the formation of these solutions were cases of peptisation and not of chemical dissolution. Davis and Farnham (*loc. cit.*) do not consider the inflexion points in the titration curves with alkalis as decisive evidence of the formation of aluminates and consider peptisation by hydroxyl ions to be responsible for the solution.

The ultrafiltrates of solutions at or beyond the inflexion point, obtained with or without addition of sodium and magnesium sulphates in sufficient quantities were analysed and their aluminium content estimated. The results are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

System.	Amount of alumina in 25 c.c.
AlCl ₃ solution ...	0.045 g.
...	0.046
Ultrafiltrate of AlCl ₃ solution (25 c.c.) + 51 c.c. 0.99 N/10-NaOH	0.045
Ultrafiltrate of AlCl ₃ solution (25 c.c.) + 51 c.c. of 0.99 N/10-NaOH + 2g. of Na ₂ SO ₄	0.045
Ultrafiltrate of AlCl ₃ solution (25 c.c.) + 60 c.c. of 0.99 N/10-NaOH	0.045
Ultrafiltrate of AlCl ₃ solution (25 c.c.) + 60 c.c. of 0.99 N/10-NaOH + 4g. of Na ₂ SO ₄	0.046
Ultrafiltrate of AlCl ₃ solution (25 c.c.) + 60 c.c. of 0.99 N/10-NaOH + 4g. of MgSO ₄	0.045

The ultrafiltrate revealed no particles when examined in the ultra-microscope, the alumina coming into the ultrafiltrate was invariably equal to the total quantity of alumina present in the aluminium chloride solution. The addition of Na₂SO₄ rules out the possibility of colloidal particles passing through the ultrafilter membrane and the results prove definitely that true solution of alumina takes place at this inflexion point.

As already mentioned, the first and the second inflexion points in the titration of solutions of aluminium chloride with NaOH correspond respectively to the precipitation and solution of alumina by the alkali. The amount of alkali (3.73 c.c. of 0.99N) required between these two inflexion points therefore has reacted with alumina (0.0184 g.) precipitated from 10 c.c. of aluminium chloride solution used. The calculated molar ratio of Al₂O₃ : NaOH is 2.05. The composition of aluminate therefore appears to be Al₂O₃.2NaOH or NaAlO₂ neglecting the difference, which is within the experimental error, of the value 2 from the experimental value 2.05.

Titration with Acids.

With Hydrochloric Acid.—Hydrous alumina sols A and C have been titrated with hydrochloric acid and the p_H , specific conductivity and chloride ion activity measured. The results for sol A are given in curves 19 and 20 (Fig. 5) and those for sol C in curves 29, 29a, 30 and 31 (Fig. 7). Titrations of HCl solutions having nearly the same p_H as that of sol have also been carried out for comparison. The results are given in curve 28 of Fig. 7. It will be found that the p_H (Fig. 5, curve 19; Fig. 7, curves 29, 30, 31), specific conductivity (Fig. 5, curve 20) and chloride ion activity (Fig. 7, curve 29a) of sols remain unchanged in the initial stage of the titra-

tion indicating that both hydrogen and chloride ions completely disappear by reaction with the surface of the colloid particles and no increase in the concentration of free ions takes place. On larger additions, the p_H decreases and the specific conductivity and the chloride ion activity increase. Table III gives the amount of HCl thus adsorbed in the initial stages of the titration during which the curves remain more or less flat.

FIG. 5.
Hydrous alumina sol A.

TABLE III.

Sol.	Alumina content.	Curve No.	Number of moles (mean of HCl adsorbed per g. mol. alumina).
A	1.37×10^{-3} g. moles/litre	19 (pot.)	0.127×10^{-3}
		20 (cond.)	0.127
C	1.25×10^{-3} g. moles/litre	29 (pot.)	0.40
		30 (pot.)	0.32
		31 (pot.)	0.32

The amount of HCl thus taken up amounts to only a very small percentage of the alumina present, but differs considerably for the two sols which is to be expected if it resulted from a surface reaction. The reaction of the sol with HCl may be looked upon as the adsorption of both H^+ and Cl^- ions in the double layer. This aspect has been discussed in Part I. According to this view aluminium hydroxide particles contain both the cation Al^{+++} and the anion AlO_2^- on their surface as the primarily adsorbed ions. The two kinds are in equilibrium, their relative proportions

FIG. 6.

Hydrous alumina sol A—titration with acids.

depending on the p_H of the system. With each addition of HCl, a new equilibrium between them is set up and further, some of the Cl^- ions and

of the excess of H^+ ions are electrically adsorbed respectively on the Al^{+++} and AlO_2^- ions on the surface. The adsorbed Cl^- ions also displace some of the OH^- ions into the solution which again neutralise the remaining H^+ ions. It appears that in the initial stages of the titration, the added H^+ and Cl^- ions disappear from the solution in this manner. The result is

FIG. 7.

Hydrous alumina sol C—titration with HCl.

interesting in connection with the study of the toxic effect of aluminium ions in acid soils. It shows that aluminium hydroxide in the colloidal state can react with H^+ ions at a p_H as high as 6.2. At higher concentrations a gradual dissolution of the particles sets in. A strong buffering is indicated near about p_H 3.5 (sol C, Fig. 7, curves 29, 30, 31). Aluminium chloride solutions with NaOH (Fig. 4, curves 16, 17, 18) also show a similar buffer action at almost the same p_H region (3.5–4.0) caused by the precipitation of the hydroxide. Dilute HCl having almost the same p_H as that of the sol also shows a strong buffering (Fig. 7. curve 28) but this is at a lower p_H (3.0). Silicic acid sol, when titrated with HCl, shows a buffering between p_H 2.5 and 3.0 (B. Chatterjee, *Proc. Indian. Sci. Cong. Assoc.*, 1942, III). Pauli and Schmidt (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 129, 199) also found that alumina sol takes up HCl at first rapidly then slowly up to about 18%.

of the alumina present. They regarded the remaining 82% as the neutral colloid' which is inert. But from what has been said above, the adsorption of HCl by alumina appears to be a reaction on the surface and not a chemical one with a fraction of the colloid particles.

With Acetic, Oxalic, Sulphuric and Phosphoric Acids.—Sols A, B and C have been titrated with solutions of the above acids. The results are expressed for sol A in Fig. 6 ; curve 21 for acetic acid ; curves 24, 25 for oxalic acid ; curves 26, 27 for sulphuric acid ; curves 22, 23 for phosphoric acid; and for sol C in Fig. 8, curves 32, 33, 34 for oxalic acid ; curves 35, 36 for phosphoric acid ; curve 37, for sulphuric acid and curve 38 for acetic acid. It will be found that the p_H decreases at first rapidly, then slowly and

FIG. 8.

Hydrous alumina sol C—titration with acids

ultimately reaches almost a constant value indicating strong buffer action. Buffering occurs at about p_H 3.5 for acetic acid ; at about p_H 3.4 for phosphoric acid ; at about p_H 3.0 for oxalic acid and at about p_H 2.8 for sulphuric acid. Measurements of the chloride ion activity of the sol (Fig. 8, curves 32a, 36a,

37a, 38a) show that all of these acids excepting acetic acid displace Cl^- ions into solution. The order of the acids in the displacement of chloride ions from the micelles by their anions is acetic < phosphoric < oxalic < sulphuric. On the addition of the acids, the anions get adsorbed and displace both Cl^- and OH^- ions into solution but the H^+ ions in solution outnumber the displaced OH^- ions and hence the p_n decreases and the chloride ion activity increases. It also shows that the acetate ions at low concentrations are not able to displace chloride ions into solution to a large extent but at large concentration, as is to be expected, some Cl^- ions are displaced. At larger concentrations gradual dissolution of the particles sets in and the p_n remains almost constant.

C O N C L U S I O N .

Potentiometric titration of the sols A, C and D with NaOH , $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$, $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ have been done. With the exception of a weak inflexion point at a lower p_n (6.25) in the case of the titration curves for sol A due to the free acid contained in it, all the titration curves show the same general features. The p_n rises sharply, at first to about 10.5 and then remains almost constant indicating a strong buffer action. Buffering is maximum at p_n 11.2 with NaOH , at p_n 11.0 with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$, and at p_n 10.8 with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$.

A weak inflexion point has been observed at p_n 12.2 and the buffer index curve shows a minimum at this point.

The amount of alumina coming into solution increases with the concentration of alkali and solution occurs at the inflexion point at p_n 12.2.

Titration of aluminium chloride with NaOH shows two inflexion points—one at p_n 7.6 and the other at p_n 10.9—corresponding respectively to the precipitation and solution of alumina by the alkali. The p_n of precipitation of alumina depends on the initial p_n of the AlCl_3 solution.

The solution of alumina in alkalis has been shown by the estimation of alumina in the ultrafiltrates from the solutions at the second inflexion point and after with or without addition of Na_2SO_4 , and MgSO_4 to be a case of true one and not of peptisation as has been supposed by some.

The ratio of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{NaOH}$ has been found to be 2.05 and hence the composition of sodium aluminate is NaAlO_2 .

HCl at small concentrations is totally adsorbed but this corresponds to only a very small fraction of the alumina present and appears to be a reaction on the surface.

A strong buffer action is observed at p_n 3.5, 3.4, 3.0⁻ and 2.8 with acetic, phosphoric, oxalic and sulphuric acids. The acids displace Cl^- ions into solution and the order of them in the displacement of chloride ions by their anions is acetic < phosphoric < oxalic < sulphuric.

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